

D 1.5

Practices to Empower Young Co-Researchers in Citizen Social Science

Learnings from youth, stakeholders, and practitioners from the joint ECSA Working group on Empowerment, inclusion, and equity (EIE WG) & YouCount webinars.

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D1.5 Practices to Empower Young Co-Researchers in Citizen Social Science

This deliverable is provided by the ECSA Working group on Empowerment, inclusion, and equity (EIE WG) jointly hosted by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Living Knowledge Network (LKN) in collaboration with OsloMet as Coordinator for the YouCount project and KTU as leader for Work package 1 (WP1) focusing on stakeholder involvement and the development of a conceptual framework for youth citizen social science (Y-CSS). It builds upon D1.1 Internet list of stakeholders, D1.2 Report on the conceptual, innovative, evaluation and ethical framework for youth citizen social science and D1.3 Report on the data collection and analysis framework and adjusted Spotteron platform, presenting conceptual and methodological frameworks for Y-CSS. This report will also inform the forthcoming D2.3 describing the experiences with hands-on YCSS in the ten local cases and D5.4 Handbook and Toolkits for youth citizen social science.

This deliverable shares our learnings on youth-centred CSS from the joint webinars by EIE WG and YouCount held in autumn 2021 and September 2023 with a particular focus on the webinar 2023. The in total four webinars were initially planned as two workshops with youths and stakeholders but were changed to digital webinars due to the pandemic and later practical reasons.

The vision of YouCount is twofold, addressing and combining both the scientific and societal needs of our time. The scientific *vision* of YouCount is to strengthen the transformative and participatory aspects of CS and social science, by enabling citizen participation in all facets, reaching out for a more egalitarian way of conducting science. The societal vision of YouCount is to contribute to create inclusive and innovative societies for European youths and to empower them in promoting active citizenship and a just and equitable future, particularly for youths with disadvantages.

Table 1: Revision history

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1.4	27/ 10 / 2023	Eglė Butkevičienė and Reidun Norvoll	Update of draft
1.5	31 / 10 / 2023	OsloMet, Reidun Norvoll	Final version submitted

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
CS	Citizen science
CSS	Citizen social science
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EIE WG	Working group on Empowerment, inclusion, and equity
EU	European Union
LKN	Living Knowledge Network
WP	Work Package
YCS	Young citizen scientist (young co- researcher) from the local community or targeted organisation or population
Y-CSS	Youth citizen social science

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Executive Summary

The main aim of this deliverable is to share learnings from four YouCount webinars in 2021 and 2023. It has been created with contributions and experiences from youth and youth co-researchers, practitioners and researchers working with youth and relevant stakeholders across 9 European countries. This collective expertise provides important insights for the design of future citizen social science projects with youth, as well as practical suggestions on how to enable and support youth to meaningfully contribute to Y-CSS.

Foreword

Dear Readers,

It is with great pleasure that we share the learnings from our webinars, jointly organised by YouCount and the EIE WG. Conducting inclusive and co-creative science with youth and stakeholders is a core ethos for YouCount and the EIE WG, and the webinars were intended to support these overarching scientific and social visions. Our last youth co-created webinar in 2023 was therefore a particularly big step forward for involving youths at the European level.

The webinars with youths and local stakeholders have contributed much knowledge to how we can and should work in practice with youths and local stakeholders when conducting hands-on citizen social science. Some important learning points for me have been the importance of building trusting relationships and creating safe and comfortable settings online and in person. I've also seen first-hand the benefit of working on longer-term collaborations, as well as how essential it is to provide support, education, and training for young co-researchers to participate equitably and meaningfully. The webinars have also supported the broader objectives and impact ambitions of the whole YouCount project. They underline our findings that the young people are active actors who use the possibilities they get through participating in the project. They are not passive recipients of benefits from science but instead take on broad roles in co-creative citizen social sciences. Being a citizen scientist is thus a dynamic process not a fixed role.

Through the webinars, I have learned more about what is inspiring and engaging for young people. Contributing towards positive social change in society is a big driver as well as the opportunity to develop cultural competencies. Moreover, it has been inspiring to learn from the rich discussions during the webinars. The expertise from EIE WG, so nicely organised by Claudia Göbel and Claire Murray, was very valuable to learn more about facilitating youth engagement at European level.

While we are extremely proud of the youth and the last webinar, we also acknowledge that there were some places that we as organisers can do better next time. We should, for example, have provided more opportunities for letting the youths learn from each other. We should not forget that research and innovation require time, enough resources, and opportunities to collaborate to succeed. Real co-creation doesn't come easy, it is not a quick fix.

Thinking about what YouCount has achieved, the webinars only provide a small snapshot of the great work by the youth and the local teams. I look forward to hearing more about this in the next months and am committed to finding ways to make opportunities like this possible in future.

Best wishes,

Prof. Reidun Norvoll

YouCount Project Coordinator

1. Introduction

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges regarding social inclusion, including (but not limited to) low social participation, unemployment, lack of social belonging, and civic engagement. There is thus a pressing need to develop more knowledge and innovation to create more inclusive and youth-friendly societies. One way to contribute to this is through Citizen Social Science with young people – Youth Citizen Social Science (Y-CSS). Still, there is limited knowledge to how we can work with co-creative CSS with and for young people, and how to increase diversity of young people participating in CSS (Healy, 2021; Constant & Hughes, 2023). This applies especially for CS outside school-settings in the local community and knowledge of possible learning outcomes for young people participating in CS projects outside formal education (Ballard, et al, 2016).

The YouCount EU project aims at developing Y-CSS and to increase inclusiveness and diversity of youth participating in CSS. To exchange knowledge for that purpose, the Working Group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness & Equity (EIE WG) worked together with the YouCount project. The EIE WG brings together practitioners of Citizen Science, community-based research and youth engagement and is supported by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Living Knowledge Network (LKN).

This deliverable combines learnings from four webinars run in 2021 and 2023, broadly covering themes connected to “Citizen Social Science with young people”. The series of joint webinars was designed to support YouCount's aim to develop hands-on Y-CSS, and to do this in close collaboration with youths and multilevel stakeholders. We had a particular focus on collaborating with underrepresented communities to develop and advance scientific approaches designed for empowerment and inclusiveness of young people. Inclusiveness and transformative impacts were therefore guiding topics and youth and YCS, stakeholders and practitioners shared their expertise and experiences. The 2021 webinars were co-created by researchers aiming to work with youth in an EU project and practitioners of participatory research (younger and older), focusing on conducting CSS more generally and on a more theoretical perspective to support the first conceptual framework (D1.2) (Göbel et al, 2021). The 2023 webinar built on the framework and lessons learned from the 2021 webinar and was instead co-created by YouCount young co-researchers to centre their perspectives and experiences. This webinar highlighted many stories of how participation in research and local innovation can benefit the youth and the research more broadly, thus highlighting the power of inclusive citizen social science.

This deliverable summarises key youth-centred learnings from the webinars and from the multiple case studies within the YouCount project to be available as resources for those who wish to be active in this space. It specifically aims to share good practice and to enable others to build on the valuable expertise that was so openly and kindly shared with us. To facilitate easy implementation and consideration of these points within other work, we are listing some of the ideas shared with us as bullet points. We would like to highlight that these webinars have already provided

important inputs to the work of the YouCount project as well as the activities of the working group.

2. Webinars Summary

The webinars were realised as a conscious co-created effort by a co-chair of the EIE working group (Claudia Göbel), an experienced youth-focused citizen science researcher (Claire Murray), a project coordinator (Reidun Norvoll) and a work package leader (Egle Butkevičienė), and many people involved in realising the webinars – YCS, presenters, co-moderators, facilitators, and technical support. The diverse sources of expertise and experience these people brought together made the rich and inspiring events possible. Names of the young people involved are included here if they were mentioned in the agendas of the webinars (see Appendix A) and beyond that only if we got explicit consent.

2.1 Overview of the webinars

We co-organised a series of webinars to create space for discussing important questions of Y-CSS, mobilise feedback on the YouCount framework & start building a community of interest around Y-CSS. Webinars' topics and formats were co-created with CSS practitioners and young researchers on a case-by-case basis. Each webinar lasted 90 minutes. The structure of the first three webinars was very similar, consisting of a keynote introduction and then followed by a series of breakout rooms and talks from youth, researchers and relevant stakeholders relating to various themes around youth in citizen science and social inclusion (Appendix A). The final webinar addressed learnings from the first three webinars and centred the youth who shared their perspectives and expertise. Some webinars/parts of the webinars are available online (youcountproject.eu), and the YouCount team have shared their notes from all of these webinars to create this document.

- **Webinar 1: Inclusive co-creation in Y-CSS: How to open up research & innovation to young people?** 24th September 2021, 68 participants
- **Webinar 2: Setting up Y-CSS: How to work in inclusive ways?** 21st October 2021, 60 participants

- **Webinar 3: Transformative & innovative impact of Y-CSS: How to make social change?** 4th November 2021, 40 participants
- **Webinar 4: Stories from the YouCount Youth – On new perspectives, being heard more deeply and belonging.** 28th September 2023, 46 participants

Participation in the webinars was open to everybody and free of charge. Invitations were shared through the mailing lists of the EIE working group, ECSA and other CSS projects as well as through YouCount channels and organisers' social media. The four webinars were only made possible by the people who invested their trust, knowledge, energy, time, critical questions, and proactive solutions into the organisation of these events.

Presenting in 2021 webinars: Aina Landsverk Hagen, Abdulaziz Alismail, Barbara Mihók, Bozenka Demeterova, Cath Larkins, Claire Murray, Finn, Fortuna Procentese, Glenn, Isabelle Freiling, Janine Adams, Jörg Matthes, Julie Ridley, Oliver Moores, Patricia Canto, Philipp Hummer, Rick Hall, Sara Berge Lorenzen, Sumaya Ali Isse, Suzanne Wilson, Usue Lorenz | **Presenting and/or Contributing in the 2023 Webinar Development:** Ákos, Andrew, Arishel, Arminas, Austėja, Biagio, Elias, Emilie, Evie, Francesca, Hamza, Jonny, Justinas, Khaleel, Moustapha, Miglé, Nedas, Regina, Yuri and Zeba. | **Breakout-room facilitating and note-taking:** Aina Landsverk Hagen, Alexandra Czeglédi, Baiba Pruse, Fredrik Brouneus, Gillian Holt, Julia Lorke, Julie Ridley, Reidun Norvoll, Sara Berge Lorenzen | **Youth experts commenting:** Katlego Nawa & 8 more experts | **Case researchers supporting co-researchers:** Susana Franco, Flora Gatti, Usue Lorenz, Sara Berge Lorenzen, Barbara Mihók, Audronė Pauliukevičiūtė, Julie Ridley, Melanie Saumer, Ileana-Maria Turda, Cathrine Skovbo Winther | **Webinar co-moderating:** Baiba Pruse, Claire Murray, Claudia Göbel, Julia Lorke | **Webinar note-taking:** Sara Berge Lorenzen | **Visual Capture:** Ruth Graham | **Technical support:** Rasmus Durban Jahr | **Webinar hosting and co-organising:** Claudia Göbel, Claire Murray, Egle Butkevičienė, Reidun Norvoll

3. Learnings

Our learnings across all webinars about how to work with young people are vast, but to support people to implement these learnings in their own practices we are presenting key learnings below. These come directly from listening to young people, local stakeholders and researchers working with youth through the webinars. We also suggest readers look at our conference proceeding from the Aarhus Engaging Citizen Science Conference. We united 25 practitioners to share their experiences planning, running and sustaining citizen social science and citizen science projects with youth (Murray et al, 2022). All of these learnings are not intended to be a definitive guide, but instead to provide a framework for building better youth-focused participatory research projects and (more importantly) better partnerships.

3.1 Insights on how to work with Youth

Youths are actually very interested in research and innovation. Different communities may have different interests in science, but youths are not necessarily hard to reach. It is about how we organise CSS projects and reach out to people. By centring the youth (and their interests), there is great potential for civic engagement and engagement in social sciences and CSS.

Recommendations for success in this from youth and other relevant parties include:

- Build trusting relationships. This was a clear recommendation from practitioners in our 2021 webinars and was a clear outcome in 2023 after the YCS and case researchers had worked together for so long.
- Creating safe and comfortable settings online and in person are important. We considered the format and content and learned from our mistakes in 2021, so we invested more time and paced the webinar for the YCS in 2023.
- Involve the YCS from the start and give them power to make decisions and meaningfully shape the work and the research questions. This was another lesson from 2021, where we realised that our webinar was not truly as youth centred as we wanted it to be, so we pivoted to a co-creation method to support this in 2023.
- Informal settings and facilitation are important – having an external facilitator can be unsettling at first, but they can also act as an advocate to shift power to youth. We had external facilitators for all webinars, and we met with them and the youth beforehand to enable them to get acquainted. We had experienced practitioners in youth citizen science and/or EIE, so they were familiar with how to shift power within traditional researcher settings to support the youth.

- Activities that are meaningful and interesting for youths can transcend traditional research methods. The importance of play and having fun should not be underestimated. We know that in our webinars, the youth particularly enjoyed having music breaks.
- Don't just focus on words: use music, pictures, and other methods to connect. This was feedback from our 2021 webinars that we addressed in our final webinar through working with Ruth Graham who visually captured the YCS's perspectives in the preparation meeting.
- Make time for the youth to get a clear understanding of the issue to be studied, what research is and their role and responsibilities as YCS. We used emails and pre-meetings to convey this to the youth, but more time should have been spent in targeting email communication to them.
- Don't forget to support and provide education and training on fundamentals of research and innovation for the YCS. Our case researchers provided this locally to the YCS and this was something the YCS valued, as shared in the webinars and in the 2023 preparation meeting (see section 4.4 and Figure 1).
- Plan engagement strategy to reach the youth by e.g., exploring existing youth groups and local links via relevant stakeholders. We invited many of these groups to our webinars but had challenges in 2021 when our project was new as we had not yet established our own network. Connecting with community leaders and experts is definitely something to be explored to achieve this.

All the above takes time, so it is very important to have a longer time perspective on such research and to allocate resources for this work. Time also enables longer term collaborations, and we have seen in YouCount how there were possibilities to include more of the local youths over the project period. They have had time to enhance self-confidence, be more secure about their role in the project, get to know each other gradually and build a network across the case countries. Being a YCS is a therefore dynamic process not a fixed role.

3.2 The role of the YCS in the YouCount CSS project

Focusing on the specific role of YCS's, there can be huge variety in their capacity to engage but also in their interests. Creating space and flexibility within CSS to respond to individual needs and interests empowers the YCS to define their own role. This can enrich the sense of ownership from the youth.

For YouCount, many YCS started out participating in data collection but expanded their expertise to include Living Lab work, discussions with local stakeholders and policymakers, creative

methods, and exhibitions. They also travelled abroad for consortium meetings and the final conference, presented their project in different forums from local to European/international, analysed data, and more.

Two important contributions to this evolving role of the YCS were the fact that the project lasted over a longer timeframe and in turn the fact that the YCS closely collaborated with the case researchers in the research teams. This supported the YCS to feel more confident in their role and to develop critical skills to influence the use of methods or contribute to research design and questions. All these factors relied on the creation of a comfortable environment for YCS from diverse backgrounds, which should not be forgotten in the design stages of new projects.

3.3 The reciprocal nature of YCS and YCS- researcher relationships

Mutual knowledge sharing and development have played a hugely important role in YouCount. As the webinar series evolved, it became clear that the participating youths/YCS are very resourceful and have identified relevant opportunities and ideas. It is thus not only a one-way relationship, where the researchers have all the information to benefit the youth. The youths' resources and contributions also support the researchers work and innovation processes. We can see here that the fundamental basis for CS in general and natural sciences (lay people help the researchers and get something back in terms of literacy etc.) actually comes into play in co-creative CSS but in a different way. Beyond supplying data and helping researchers to perform the study, they also share other perspectives, insights and contribute with information to local stakeholders and policymakers, partake actively in innovation processes on local and national levels and contribute with suggestions to new social innovations. With this exchange of ideas and knowledge, a mutual and reciprocal relationship of support can grow. In the case of YouCount, the potential of joint work between professional and non-professional researchers as a core element in citizen science was so vividly evident in the webinar in September 2023 (as visually captured by Ruth Graham during the pre-meeting with the youth, **Error! Reference source not found.**), so creating space for these conversations is important.

Figure 1 - Visual capture of YouCount YCS's feelings on working with case researchers.

3.4 How to engage young people in CSS projects at a European level

Uniting youths, stakeholders, researchers, and others across different times zones is not a trivial affair. This is particularly the case when it the unusual setting of YouCount in communities meant that many of our YCS were participating around work, school, and other activities/responsibilities. Working at the European level therefore takes extra time and effort, especially when collaborating with underrepresented or underserved groups. We would argue that the key investment in a successful CSS-YCS project is time, due to the vital need to build strong relationships and trust with the youth. As an example, for our final webinar in 2023, we spent on average 6 hours per case researcher working with our YCS, but this comes on top of the many hours we had all invested in building up collaborative relationships.

Supporting and platforming the views of YCS at a European level is more than just providing them with a space to present. It relies on confidence in presenting, understanding what should be presented and how to target information at audiences, what the research question being explored is etc. We built up layers of support to empower the YCS for this, through facilitators who centred their needs, case researchers who provided emotional support and opportunities to practise and

chances to define the topics under discussion (at least in the final webinar). It is easy for researchers to take these considerations for granted, given that much of their work assumes a high-level of competency in these areas. It is therefore important to have preparation meetings at both a local and a collective European level to support YCS to deliver their ideas and thoughts in a way that truly reflects their power. It also should not be forgotten that English is not a native language for most European youth, even if it is frequently used as the common language of communication. Opportunities to present in native languages (with translation) or support with the language of presentation should be provided. In the case of YouCount, pastoral support was provided by the case researchers who supported when needed, but otherwise deferred to the youth. The facilitator can also play an important role here as a pace setter, to support the YCS with time to translate for themselves but also to centre their perspectives in an environment that traditionally does not centre youth.

3.5 What do young people gain from being a YCS

An early consideration in any CSS should be what do participants gain from participating in the research. YouCount is exploring this through impact and evaluation dimensions in WP 4 Evaluation study, WP2 and 3 Case experiences to see to what extent participating in the project and as a YCS can benefit the individual youth and how. However, from our webinars, we have identified numerous possible benefits for the youths from being a YCS (see for example Figure 2), especially for those working in the research teams over a longer timeframe. These benefits were shared with us through the webinars and also locally in conversations with case researchers. These benefits expand the traditional focus in CS on science literacy.

These are, for example:

- More science literacy and knowledge of the study topic
- Developing broader skills and capacities: learning English and training to present in English in local to international, presenting at local and national levels. This also builds self-confidence.
- Being able to travel and meet cross borders.
- Developing cultural competence by learning more about other countries and their cultures, partaking more in cross-cultural settings etc.
- Building social networks between youths but also in the community with local stakeholders and researchers. They are also building networks with academics etc. in other countries. This has opened other possibilities for them in the local community.

- Using the capacities and participation to increase employability and to get jobs: the work as YCS is a job itself, it can be used on CV and be more attractive on the job market. This also creates economic impact by having incomes etc.
- Creating new possibilities for civic engagement and a sense of having a say: talking with local policymakers/stakeholders and media etc.
- Access to new social roles, arenas and social fellowships supporting empowerment through their participation in a project, which can be empowering.

Figure 2 - Visual capture of YouCount YCS's perspectives on what they learned taking part in YouCount.

VISUAL CAPTURE
by RUTHGRAHAM.IE

3.6 Incentives for youth, participating in a CSS project

The incentives for participation for youth have been a theme that we have reflected on throughout the YouCount project. Incentives can be a motivation to participate, but they are not always immediately obvious or visible. The list below details some of the incentives shared with us by the youth and other parties, highlighting the broad range of opportunities that a CSS project presents.

- The importance of travel opportunities
- The importance of meeting other youths from other countries. The travel dimensions may also be extra valuable for those who cannot afford this in their private life.
- The importance of being able to learn something new.
- The interest in a research topic/to contribute to positive social change.
- To be part of a social fellowship.

- To be able to have a contributory role.
- To get access to other social arenas and networks.
- Compensation for their time (where possible).

Some of these insights were also visually captured during the pre-meeting with the YCS in the fourth webinar (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Visual capture of YouCount YCS's perspectives on what they found interesting whilst taking part in YouCount.

3.7 Specific Recommendations for working online inclusively with Youth

The process of organising and co-creating the webinars highlighted good practices for working with YCS and youth online. There should be a strong emphasis on methods, preparation, and training time, especially for researchers and discussion facilitators. Aim to sensitise the team to operate in an open group not assuming other researchers as interlocutors, people familiar with how EU research projects work or what Citizen Science is. It is also important to remain flexible and adapt infrastructure and processes for each webinar based on comments and critiques.

Whilst there are many challenges to creating a safe and engaging environment for young people online, there are numerous benefits that our YCS shared including: meeting other YCS from

different countries, learning about different cultures and gaining presentation experience. What follows is a list of recommendations that comes from the organisers, case researchers, practitioners, stakeholders and, crucially from the young co-researchers themselves.

- Develop a safe space policy. We developed one for our first webinar and modified it as necessary.
- Ensure there is local support for the YCS. Our case researchers locally supported the YCS, providing translation and pastoral care to prepare for meetings.
- Set the pace of the webinar to reflect the comfort and confidence of the YCS. Our facilitators led this, trying to give the YCS time to convey their ideas and manage the flow of the webinar.
- Include the YCS in the event creation. We learnt from our webinars in 2021, where the youth were not involved from the start. Our 2023 webinar centred the youth and together we co-created the webinar structure, evaluation and themes.
- Peer support – whether through groups or through working with case researchers – is important for youth in unknown spaces. In our 2021 and 2023 webinars, we discovered that our YCS felt most at ease when they could work with others that they knew. For most of the webinars the case researchers were on hand, but some YCS also preferred to present in a group.
- YCS need to get enough information to participate meaningfully. We invested time in explaining the aims of the webinars through initial emails and in our pre-meeting to ensure our YCS understood and had time to formulate relevant insights.
- Essential to listen to what people actually have to say, rather than treating them as representatives of a too generalised category, such as “youth” or “young people”. This feedback came from one of our webinars in 2021, where we had important conversations on intersectionality and how people define themselves.
- Consider the structure of the online meeting/event and plan for enough breaks and for enough icebreakers. We had feedback that our webinars were generally too long for the youth, with breaks that were not long enough. We suggest having shorter events up to one hour to maximise comfort.
- Consider communication and language – what information gets to the YCS and how. Our emails to the youth were sometimes too long and too complicated.
- Invest in preparation to ensure YCS feel comfortable, confident, and ready for the event. For all events we had a pre-meeting to introduce everyone, to manage expectations (both ours and the youths) and to communicate the webinar structure and timing. Many of our case researchers also met with the YCS to discuss the webinar and provide support to practise if necessary.
- Create independent spaces for young people. This was a request from the youth, but we did not achieve this fully in our webinars. We tried to create a youth-led space during the co-creation of the final webinar in 2023, but this was not fully independent.

- Involve relevant stakeholders but prioritise the YCS/youth. We had lots of stakeholders involved but in the early stage of the project, we did not have enough experience or contacts to fully centre the youth. We tried to address this by co-creating the final webinar and focusing on their interests and questions.
- Provide support for individual needs e.g., language support or accessibility adaptations. We paced our webinars to support those speaking English as a foreign language (the majority of our YCS) and also ensured those who needed more time had it.

4. Conclusion

The webinars showed that there is a great potential for youth civic engagement and engagement in social sciences and CSS, by:

- centring the youth interests,
- building trusting relationships,
- creating safe and comfortable environments,
- giving them power to make decisions and shape the work and the research questions
- engaging them in activities that are meaningful for them,
- creating opportunities for networking and learning,
- providing incentives and appropriate rewards for their engagement.

The lessons learned from the YouCount webinars confirm many findings from other CS studies about what are important engagement and motivational factors when involving young people in (citizen) science, and to increase diversity of young participants (see e.g., Constant and Hughes, 2023 and Healy, 2021).

However, our experiences highlight the importance – not at least for those often further away from science – of establishing practices that centre youth empowerment from the start. This includes investing in building relationships, providing time to develop a safe role as YCS, peer support, as well as a committed and structured way of working over a longer period, and thoroughly facilitation, to succeed. This particularly applies to Y-CSS at European or international levels, where young people may experience many barriers for participation that need to be dealt with, for example, language, translation, social and technical support and more.

These factors highlight the need for developing good infrastructures for inclusive and participatory CSS, and for providing enough resources for involvement. These pre-requisites for successful hands-on Y-CSS should be an important focus in future science policy and CSS development.

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Appendixes

Table 3: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
Appendix A	Webinar Agendas	21

Appendix A

A.1 Agenda of first webinar

Webinar 1 on inclusive co-creation in Y-CSS:

How to open up research & innovation to young people?

Friday 24th September 2021, 13:00-15:00 CEST

Agenda

13:00 Welcome by YouCount & EIE WG, idea of webinar, safe space, introduction

Reidun Norvoll, YouCount coordinator at OsloMet

Claudia Göbel, EIE WG co-chair

Claire Murray, ECSA

13:15 What is important for working together?

Experiences from Nottingham

Rick Hall, ignite! education charity in Nottingham

Bozenka Demeterova, youth worker in Sneinton, Nottingham

Finn, SKATE Nottingham group

Experiences from Oslo

Sumaya Ali Isse, young researcher

Aziz Alismail, young researcher

Glenn, Tøyen Unlimited, Oslo
Sara Berge Lorenzen, OsloMet

Experiences from Lancaster

Oliver Moores, UCan research group
Cath Larkins, The Centre for Children and Young People's Participation at
UCLan

Questions & Answers after each input

14:10 Breakout groups on questions by young researchers

14:40 Round of reflections on presentations & breakout groups by participants in plenary

15:00 Farewell

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges with regard to social inclusion (e.g., social participation, employment, social belonging). There is a pressing need to develop more knowledge and innovation to create more inclusive and youth-friendly societies. One way to contribute to this is through Citizen Social Science with young people - **Youth Citizen Social Science (Y-CSS)**.

As practitioners of Citizen Science, community-based research and youth engagement, we seek to use this series of webinars to **create space for discussing important questions of Y-CSS**, mobilise feedback on the YouCount framework & start building a community of interest around Y-CSS.

Participation is open to everybody and free of charge. The webinars are organised by the Working Group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness & Equity at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Living Knowledge Network (LKN) together with the YouCount EU project.

A. 2 Agenda of second webinar

Webinar 2 on setting up Y-CSS: How to work in inclusive ways?

Thursday 21st October 2021, 13:00-15:00 CEST

Agenda

13:00 Welcome by YouCount & EIE WG, idea of webinar, safe space, introduction

Reidun Norvoll, YouCount coordinator at OsloMet

Claudia Göbel, EIE WG co-chair

Baiba Pruse, Ca'Foscari University of Venice, co-moderation

13:15 Practically Preparing for Youth Participation, Claire Murray, ECSA SEEDs project, 15mins + 5mins Q&A

13:35 From proposal to implementation: Introducing the YouCount multiple case study approach, Julie Ridley, UCLan, 10mins + 5mins Q&A

13:50 Breakout groups for discussion of specific aspects of the YouCount framework

10 mins input by YouCount partner on the question that they seek to address;

35 mins discussion in group.

(1) Co-Evaluating citizen social science – across cases and countries and across citizens and professional scientists

Isabelle Freiling & Jörg Matthes, University Vienna

Facilitator: Baiba Pruse, Ca'Foscari University of Venice

(2) How to do inclusive communication from the start?

Barbara Mihók, ESSRG

Facilitator: Alexandra Czeglédi, ESSRG

(3) How to create inclusive spaces and relations for young people from diverse backgrounds?

Suzanne Wilson, UCLan

Fortuna Procentese, UNINA

Facilitator: Julie Ridley, UCLan

(4) Engaging with young people for YouCount webinars - how to build on what we have learned so far?

Reidun Norvoll, YouCount coordinator, OsloMet & Sumaya Ali Isse

Facilitator: Sara Berge Lorenzen, OsloMet

14:40 What do you take home? Round of impressions from discussions in plenary

15:00 Farewell

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges with regard to social inclusion (e.g., social participation, employment, social belonging). There is a pressing need to develop more knowledge and innovation to create more inclusive and youth-friendly societies. One way to contribute to this is through Citizen Social Science with young people - **Youth Citizen Social Science (Y-CSS)**.

This webinar seeks to **mobilise feedback and inputs for setting up the YouCount project**. Members of the project are developing a framework for Y-CSS for setting up case studies in several countries in a good way, i.e., to translate Y-CSS into practical research and innovations. They will present their concepts and seek your feedback on how the local projects can be designed including: How to **work in inclusive ways with youths and local stakeholders**? What are **dos and don'ts** based on your experiences? How to **co-evaluate outcomes and impact** of local projects?

As practitioners of Citizen Science, community-based research and youth engagement, we seek to use this series of webinars to **create space for discussing important questions of Y-CSS**, mobilise feedback on the YouCount framework & start building a community of interest around Y-CSS. **Participation is open to everybody and free of charge**. The webinars are organised by the Working Group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness & Equity at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Living Knowledge Network (LKN) together with the YouCount EU project.

A.3 Agenda of third webinar

Webinar 3 on transformative & innovative impact of Y-CSS:

How to make social change?

Thursday 4th November 2021, 13:00-15:00 CET

Agenda

13:00 Welcome by YouCount & EIE WG, idea of webinar, safe space, introduction

Egle Butkevičienė, KTU, YouCount

Claudia Göbel, EIE WG co-chair (moderation)

Julia Lorke, IPN Kiel (co-moderation)

13:15 Making change and measuring impact in YouCount, Usue Lorenz & Patricia Canto, Orkestra
- Deusto Foundation, YouCount, 20mins + 20mins Q&A

14:00 Breakout groups for discussion of specific aspects of the YouCount framework

(1) Social belonging through participation

Egle Butkevičienė, KTU

facilitated by tbc.

(2) How to build an app for impact in Citizen Social Science?

Philipp Hummer, SPOTTERON

facilitated by Reidun Norvoll, OsloMet

(3) Designing children-youth involved research for making a social change in the community

Suzanne Wilson, UCLan

Janine Adams, Furness Multicultural Community Forum

facilitated by Julia Lorke, IPN Kiel

14:40 Round of reflections on discussions by participants in plenary
with comments by Sumaya Ali Isse & Reidun Norvoll

15:00 Farewell

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges with regard to social inclusion (e.g., social participation, employment, social belonging). There is a pressing need to develop more knowledge and innovation to create more inclusive and youth-friendly societies. One way to contribute to this is through Citizen Social Science with young people - **Youth Citizen Social Science (Y-CSS)**. This webinar looks at **Y-CSS, innovation and increasing its transformative potential**: How to create innovations and positive social change? How should we work to be transformative? What is needed?

As practitioners of Citizen Science, community-based research and youth engagement, we seek to use this series of webinars to **create space for discussing important questions of Y-CSS**, mobilise feedback on the YouCount framework & start building a community of interest around Y-CSS. **Participation is open to everybody and free of charge.** The webinars are organised by the Working Group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness & Equity at the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and the Living Knowledge Network (LKN) together with the YouCount EU project.

A.4 Agenda of fourth webinar

Webinar 4: Stories from the YouCount Youth - On new perspectives, being heard more deeply and belonging.

Thursday 28th September 2023, 17.30-19.00 CET

Presenters

Austėja, Justinas and Miglė in Lithuania (in conversation with Audronė)

Moustapha and Hamza in Spain

Ákos and Regina in Hungary (in conversation with Barbara)

Emilie in Denmark (in discussion with Cathrine)

Francesca, Yuri and Biagio in Italy

Elias in Norway (in discussion with Sara)

Andrew, Arishel, Evie and Khaleel in the United Kingdom

YouCount is working to co-create new knowledge and innovations to increase youth social inclusion. Since 2020, 100s of young people from local communities and 30 students from universities have worked with researchers on 10 research questions in 9 different countries. This webinar is a unique opportunity for you to learn about the YouCount project. 16 of these young people co-created this webinar and some of them will share their stories from the YouCount project. This includes lessons learned and what you should consider for future work with youth

like them. Join us to learn about their important work, their results, and their valuable perspectives on engaging youth in citizen social science.

This webinar is co-created by the YouCount Youth, and co-organized by the YouCount team and the ECSA and the Living Knowledge Network Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity Working Group.

Please note that we hope to publish the webinar creation process, learnings, and evaluation as a case study with the youth as co-authors.

YouCount

Youth Citizen Science

PARTNERS:

